

Machine Learning With Homomorphic Encryption For Linear Regression Model

Adarsh V
PG Scholar
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering, Kanjirappally
Kottayam, India
adarshv2022a@mca.ajce.in

Lisha Varghese
Asst. Professor
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering, Kanjirappally
Kottayam, India
lishavarghese@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—Machine learning jobs typically choose to transfer data and models to a third-party server to take use of cloud computing's compute and storage capability. Third-party servers, on the other hand, may experience data privacy breaches throughout the collection, storage, and use of data, particularly in the domains of finance, medical treatment, and biometrics. In the cipher-text domain, homomorphic encryption technology allows for cipher-text calculation without decryption and can be utilized for machine learning model training and prediction.

Keywords— *homomorphic encryption, machine learning, linear regression, python-paillier package*

I. INTRODUCTION

Let's start with a basic Machine Learning (ML) algorithm that takes our data as input and produces a conclusion - a classification label, a numerical value, or a suggestion. The privacy issue arises from the fact that we must provide our personal information in order to receive such helpful and beneficial predictions. Data privacy can be safeguarded by encrypting it. Standard encryption algorithms, on the other hand, do not allow computation on encrypted data. This is where Homomorphic Encryption (HE) comes in handy.

II. DESCRIPTION

The following diagram attempts to convey an intuitive understanding of what Homomorphic Encryption entails.

Fig. 1 - Homomorphic Encryption in Machine Learning

1. Put your gold in a locked box.
2. Keep the key.
3. Let your jeweler work on it through a glove box.
4. Unlock the box when the jeweler is done!

Even if the model is housed in the cloud, there is still a privacy/IP issue. External organization must either contribute their input data (such as photographs to be

classified) or download the model in order to use it. From a privacy standpoint, uploading input data can be troublesome. In this case, one possible solution is to encrypt the data in such a way that one organization can utilize a model owned by another without revealing their IP to each other.

III. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

A. Importance

Homomorphic encryption is an example of a technology with potential in the cloud. The goal is to safeguard and manage data from users of a client business who want to store it on untrustworthy public clouds.

Working with encrypted data is also computationally difficult and storage-heavy, therefore high-speed data processing alternatives in the cloud can be used to improve performance.

B. Problem Definition

The issue of maintaining privacy has recently become one of the most practical difficulties for machine learning. The PPML server can complete all of the computations required in the desired service before giving the encrypted result to the client if the client transmits the public keys and encrypted data to it using an FHE technique. As a result, the use of FHEs to PPML has already been widely investigated.

C. Linear Regression

The least squares method can be used in linear regression to discover the linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Simple regression is used when there is only one independent variable, and multiple linear regression is used when there are two or more independent variables. The distribution relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is the subject of regression analysis. When the sample includes a lot of features, however, solving the parameters one by one using the algebraic derivation method will take longer. Other machine learning algorithms require greater computer

resources to forecast higher models. We're going to use a simpler model that only has four features.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Jiss Varghese and Lisha Varghese[1] Proposed a method that is, Sensitive data must be encrypted before being uploaded into global space to avoid problems with secrecy. As a result, performing effective keyword-based search and retrieval across these encrypted data becomes a challenge. To circumvent this, a Two Step Searchable Encryption (TSSE) approach that provides multikeyword based top-k data retrieval has been proposed.

Bijiao Chen and Xianghan Zheng[2] Cloud-based machine learning can improve training capabilities and reduce costs. Typically, data and models are uploaded to a third-party server for machine learning operations. These server may face data privacy leaks in the process of data storage and use, This can be solved using homomorphic encryption

J. h. cheon and J. kim[3] To lower the storage needs of most somewhat or fully homomorphic encryption (FHE) applications, introduce a hybrid homomorphic encryption that combines public-key encryption (PKE) and somewhat homomorphic encryption (SHE). In this, messages are encrypted with a PKE and computations on encrypted data are carried out using SHE or FHE after homomorphic decryption, It shows efficient homomorphic decryption

S. gupta and G. arora[4] Proposed a method of using homomorphic encryption in its current state of properties to enable run-time location privacy. This is done in conjunction with the Global Positioning System, which employs satellites to calculate the user's coordinates.

M. Mohan, M. K. K. Devi and V. J. Prakash[5] Done a detailed survey on the various homomorphic encryption scheme based on the parameter involved, the encryption decryption mechanisms, their homomorphic properties, security considerations etc. These encryption methods with homomorphic property are much suitable for applications that require data privacy and security.

V. SYSTEM DESIGN

Tools & Processing

A. Python

Python is a general-purpose, high-level, interpreted programming language. It prioritizes code readability and makes considerable use of indentation in its design philosophy. Python is garbage-collected and dynamically typed. Here python version 3.9.1 is used for the implementation

B. Pycharm

PyCharm is a dedicated Python Integrated Development Environment (IDE) providing a wide range of essential tools

for Python developers, tightly integrated to create a convenient environment for productive Python, web, and data science development.

C. Django Web Framework

Django is a server-side web framework built in Python that is very popular and has a lot of features. This module explains why Django is so popular as a web server framework. It's employed in the user interface design.

D. python-paillier

Python-paillier is a partly homomorphic encryption library based on the paillier algorithm. Only non-negative numbers less than PaillierPublicKey.n are defined as Paillier encryption. EncodedNumber implements an encoding strategy for floating point and signed integers that is consistent with the Paillier cryptosystem's partially homomorphic characteristics.

1. $D(E(a) * E(b)) = a + b$
2. $D(E(a)**b) = a * b$

If a and b are ints or floats, E stands for encoding, followed by encryption, and D stands for decryption, followed by decoding.

The homomorphic properties of the paillier crypto system are:

- ✧ Encrypted numbers can be multiplied by a non encrypted scalar.
- ✧ Encrypted numbers can be added together.
- ✧ Encrypted numbers can be added to non encrypted scalars.

VI. METHODOLOGY

Assume that we are the server and that we have certain information. We begin by defining and training a model using training data. Then we contact a client that has some of their own data and would like to use your model to make some predictions with it.

In this analysis we give a quick overview of the system and discuss how homomorphic encryption can be used to tackle problems with machine learning algorithms.

In this model we are trying to predict somebody salary based on some numerical facts about them such as their Age, healthy_eating, active_lifestyle, Gender.

Fig. 2 - Diagram showing the proposed method

Where D is the data given, R is the predicted result

E(D) - Encrypted data
E(R) - Encrypted Result

Step 1: Encrypt the user data with a public and private key

```
public_key, private_key = paillier.generate_paillier_keypair()
keys={}
keys['public_key'] = {'n': public_key.n}
keys['private_key'] = {'p': private_key.p, 'q': private_key.q}
with open('custkeys.json', 'w') as file:
    json.dump(keys, file)
```

Fig. 3 - Generating Private and Public keys

```
data = [int(age),int(h),int(a),int(g)]
serializeData(pub_key, data)
datafile=serializeData(pub_key, data)
with open('data.json', 'w') as file:
    json.dump(datafile, file)
```

Fig. 4 - Encrypting the data

Step 2: Predicting the salary using linear regression model that is already created

```
mycoef=LinModel().getCoef()
pk=data['public_key']
pubkey= paillier.PaillierPublicKey(n=int(pk['n']))
enc_nums_rec = [paillier.EncryptedNumber(pubkey, int(x[0]), int(x[1])) for x in data['values']]
results=sum([mycoef[i]*enc_nums_rec[i] for i in range(len(mycoef))])
```

Fig. 5 - Multiplying the ciphertext with model co-efficient

Step 3: Decrypting the predicted result

```
results, pubkey = computeData()
encrypted_data={}
encrypted_data['pubkey'] = {'n': pubkey.n}
encrypted_data['values'] = (str(results.ciphertext()), results.exponent)
serialized = json.dumps(encrypted_data)
return serialized
```

Fig. 6 - Decrypting the result

VII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 7 - User Input Interface

Fig. 8 - Encrypted Result

Fig. 9 - Decrypted Result

Now we are going to predict the salary without encrypting the data in pycharm

```
data=age, he, al, gen = [45,7,8,1]
mycoef=LinModel().getCoef()
print("prediction")
print(sum([data[i]*mycoef[i] for i in range(len(data))])
```

Fig. 10 - Predicting using the plaintext data

Fig. 10.1 - Predicted Result

As you can see the Predicted value using plaintext data and the cipher text data is the same and we got a accuracy of around

0.8378741174877536

Working with encrypted data is also computationally difficult and storage-heavy, therefore high-speed data processing alternatives in the cloud can be used to improve performance.

VIII. CONCLUSION

When the homomorphic encryption algorithm is secure and the Cloud is unable to access the user's private key, it is unable to extract the plaintext data from the ciphertext data, ensuring that the plaintext data is secure. we can infer that it is possible and viable to apply homomorphic encryption to machine learning without influencing accuracy. It is reasonable for application situations with high security requirements.

IX. REFERENCES

- [1] Jiss Varghese, Lisha Varghese , " Homomorphic Encryption for Multi-keyword based Search and Retrieval over Encrypted Data " , International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management (IJAIEM), Volume 3, Issue 8, August 2014 , pp. 138-146 , ISSN 2319 - 4847.
- [2] Bijiao Chen, Xianghan Zheng, Implementing Linear Regression with Homomorphic Encryption, Procedia Computer Science, Volume 202, 2022, Pages 324-329, ISSN 1877-0509
- [3] J. h. cheon and J. kim, "a hybrid scheme of public-key encryption and somewhat homomorphic encryption," in iee transactions on information forensics and security, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 1052-1063, may 2015, doi: 10.1109/tifs.2015.2398359.
- [4] S. gupta and G. arora, "use of homomorphic encryption with gps in location privacy," 2019 4th international conference on information systems and computer networks (iscon), 2019, pp. 42-45, doi: 10.1109/iscon47742.2019.9036149.
- [5] M. Mohan, M. K. K. Devi and V. J. Prakash, "Homomorphic encryption-state of the art," 2017 International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control (I2C2), 2017, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/I2C2.2017.8321774.
- [6] J. -W. Lee et al., "Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning With Fully Homomorphic Encryption for Deep Neural Network," in IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 30039-30054, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3159694.
- [7] H. wang and F. hao, "an efficient linear regression classifier," 2012 iee international conference on signal processing, computing and control, 2012, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ispcc.2012.6224355.
- [8] <https://blog.openmined.org/encrypted-deep-learning-classification-with-pysyft/>
- [9] Manoj Kumar Mohanty, "Secure Data Storage on the Cloud using Homomorphic Encryption";(NIT, Rourkela 2013)
- [10] <https://github.com/satssehgal/Homomorphic-Encryption>